

Diazoketones from Salicyl and Cinnamoyl Chlorides

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1-Diazo-4-phenyl-3-butenone and 1-diazo-1-methyl-4-phenyl-3-butenone have been prepared from cinnamoyl chloride (1 mol.) and diazomethane (2.5 mols.) and diazoethane (2.5 mols.) respectively. Salicyl chloride (1 mol.) with diazomethane [2.5 mols. and 4 mols. (excess)] gives a mixture of ω -diazo-*o*-hydroxyacetophenone and ω -diazo-*o*-methoxyacetophenone. All these diazoketones have been identified.

Acid chlorides like salicyl and cinnamoyl chlorides contain two sites of reactivity towards diazomethane. By using different amounts of diazomethane [4 mols. (excess) and 2.5 mols.] per molecule of cinnamoyl chloride, several workers (Wotiz and Bucu, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1955, 20, 210; Grundmann and Frischmann, *Annalen*, 1945 524, 31; Moore, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1955, 20, 1607) obtained a mixture containing 4-phenyl-5-diazoacetylpyrazoline and 1-diazo-4-phenyl-3-butenone in different amounts. The diazoketones so obtained have been subjected to some of their well-known reactions (Moore, *loc. cit.*; Wotiz and Bucu, *loc. cit.*). We prepared 1-diazo-4-phenyl-3-butenone (I:R=H) and 1-diazo-1-methyl-4-phenyl-3-butenone (I:R=Me) from cinnamoyl chloride (1*M*) and diazomethane and diazoethane (2.5*M*) respectively in ether solution at 0°.

Although the ketone (I:R=H) has been described (Wotiz and Bucu, *loc. cit.*; Moore, *loc. cit.*) we found that our sample, after crystallisation twice from ethanol, melted at 177° (Wotiz and Bucu, *loc. cit.*, report m. p. 173°). Moreover, we could accomplish the Arndt and Eistert synthesis (*Ber.*, 1935, 68, 204) with ammonia using Ag₂O as a catalyst and obtained an amide (II), m.p. 129° (Kohl, *Ber.*, 1903, 36, 174, reports m.p. 130°), which involved Wolff's rearrangement (*Annalen*, 1912, 394, 40). The compound (I:R=H) on treatment with ethanolic KOH (Yates and Shapiro, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 212) gave cinnamic acid and ammonia, indicating the presence of a double bond.

The diazoketone (I:R=Me) on crystallisation from ethanol melted at 170°. When subjected to the Arndt and Eistert synthesis, it gave α -methyl- γ -phenylvinylacetic acid (III), m.p. 109° (Fittig and Liebmann, *Annalen*, 1882, 255, 262, report m.p. 110.5°). Treatment of (I:R=Me) with ethanolic KOH gave cinnamic acid (Yates and Shapiro, *loc. cit.*).

2-Hydroxy-3-naphthoylchloride on treatment with diazomethane affords 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoyldiazomethane (Krzikalla and Eistert, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1935, *ii*, 143, 50). Thus in the formation of this diazoketone, methylation of phenolic group does not take place. We found, however, that salicyl chloride (1*M*) on treatment with diazomethane (2.5*M* and 4*M*) respectively gave a mixture of ω -diazo-*o*-hydroxyacetophenone (IV) and ω -diazo-*o*-methoxyacetophenone (V). The formation of the mixture of the diazoketones (IV) and (V) is quite similar to that of the mixture of 1-diazo-4-phenyl-3-butenone and 4-phenyl-5-diazoacetylpyrazoline (*loc. cit.*). Thus the phenolic group was methylated in both the cases, but the amount of the latter was found to be more than that of the former when 4 mols. of diazomethane were used. The ether solution containing the diazoketones after keeping overnight gave a violet coloration with ferric chloride, indicating the presence of a phenolic group. The solution was concentrated by removing some solvent. When 4 mols. of diazomethane were used, the excess of diazomethane distilled with ether. The ether solution was treated with 1% NaOH solution, when ω -diazo-*o*-hydroxyacetophenone dissolved in aqueous layer as its sodium compound. The aqueous layer was divided into three portions. One portion was kept for 24 hours, which on acidification gave salicylic acid, m. p. 158° (Yates and Shapiro, *loc. cit.*), thus proving the presence of a phenolic group in the diazoketone (IV). The second portion was immediately just acidified with HCl (dil.) and extracted with ether. The ether extract gave coumaranone (VI), m. p. 104° (Bose and Yates, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 4703). The formation of coumaranone can be explained by the mechanism described by Bose and Yates (*loc. cit.*). The third portion of the aqueous layer was subjected to the Arndt and Eistert synthesis (*loc. cit.*), when the sodium compound of *o*-hydroxyphenylacetamide (VII) was obtained, from which it was isolated on acidification with dilute acetic acid, m. p. 116° (Stoermer, *Annalen*, 1900, **313**, 86, reports m. p. 116-17°). The amide on hydrolysis gave *o*-hydroxyphenylacetic acid (VIII), m. p. 137° (Pschorr *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1900, **33**, 166, report m. p. 137°).

The above reactions completely establish the identity of ω -diazo-*o*-hydroxyacetophenone (IV).

The ether solution left after treatment with 1% NaOH did not give any coloration with ferric chloride. On removal of the ether a liquid was obtained, a portion of which on treatment with dilute HCl gave coumaranone (VI), m. p. 104° (Bose and Yates, *loc. cit.*).

The other portion, when subjected to the Arndt and Eistert synthesis, gave, as expected, *o*-methoxyphenylacetamide (IX), m.p. 131° (Seth and Deshapande, this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 429, report m.p. 131°). This confirmed the identity of ω -diazoo-*o*-methoxyacetophenone.

The formation of some ω -diazoo-*o*-methoxyacetophenone from 2.5 mols. of diazomethane is as expected. But the existence of ω -diazoo-*o*-hydroxyacetophenone, even when 4 mols. of diazomethane are used, is noteworthy.

EXPERIMENTAL

Diazoketones (I: R=H; R=Me) were prepared from cinnamoyl chloride (1 mol., 8.5 g.) and diazomethane and diazoethane (each 2.5 mols., 5.5 g. and 7.0 g. respectively) in ether solution at 0°. The diazoketones were thrown out on evaporation of some of the solvent.

1-Diazo-4-phenyl-3-butenone (I: R=H) was crystallised twice from ethanol, m.p. 177° (Found: C, 69.1; H, 5.28; N, 15.9. C₁₀H₈ON₂ requires C, 69.7; H, 4.6; N, 16.2%).

It gave with ammonia and AgNO₃ β -benzylidenepropionamide. It crystallised from hot water, m.p. 129°.

The diazoketone (I: R=H), when treated with aqueous ethanolic KOH, gave cinnamic acid, m.p. 133°. A mixed melting point showed no depression.

1-Diazo-1-methyl-4-phenyl-3-butenone (I: R=Me) was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 170°. (Found: C, 70.2; H, 4.9; N, 14.6. C₁₁H₁₀ON₂ requires C, 70.9; H, 5.3; N, 15.05%).

When subjected to the Arndt and Eistert synthesis, it gave α -methyl- γ -phenylvinylacetic acid, crystallised from hot water, m. p. 109°. (Found: Equiv., 175.5. C₁₁H₁₂O₂ requires equiv., 176).

The diazoketone (I: R=Me), when treated with aqueous ethanolic KOH, gave cinnamic acid, m. p. 133° (undepressed by mixed m.p.).

ω -Diazoo-*o*-hydroxyacetophenone (IV) and ω -Diazoo-*o*-methoxyacetophenone (V).—Salicyl chloride (1 mol., 6.4 g.) was treated with diazomethane (2.5 mols., 4.4 g. and 4 mols., 6.8 g. respectively) at 0°. The ether solutions were concentrated by distillation and extracted with 1% NaOH solution. Both aqueous and ethereal layers were treated with the results described earlier (*vide supra*).

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